

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****DIABETES INSPIDUS IN CHILDREN**¹Dr Farah Rao,²Dr Hafsa Shabbir,³Dr Hafza Sarah Tariq
^{1,2,3}MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020

Diabetes insipidus is defined as incapability to focus urine secondary to vasopressin deficiency or to vasopressin resistance which outcome is polyuria. The prevalence of DI is approximately 1:25,000 less than 10% of cases are hereditary naturally. Certainly diabetes insipidus is very infrequent. More than 90% of reported cases are from Central DI (CDI) depending on the cause it can occur at any age. Since now no hereditary prevalence of CDI has been confirmed. Whereas Nephrogenic DI is less resistant than CDI. DI can be defined as CDI or NDI [1]. In the magnocellular neurons of the paraventricular and supraoptic nuclei of the hypothalamus Vasopressin is produced which send axons to the posterior pituitary. The vasopressin is then excreted into the bloodstream via posterior pituitary. The neurons which release vasopressin are damaged in case of CDI. Whereas in case of NDI, there is normal production of vasopressin but at kidney level there is no response of the hormone. At the basolateral membrane of the collecting duct of the kidney Vasopressin acts at V2 receptors. Management of DI in patients requiring intravenous fluids needs further attention as no evidence based studies exist to determine optimal fluid choice and fluid rates. NDI is currently managed with thiazide diuretics; however additional research is necessary to optimize management and promising alternatives are on the horizon.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Farah Rao,**
MBBS, Nawaz Sharif Medical College, Gujrat.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Farah Rao et al., *Diabetes Insipidus In Children* ., *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2020; 07(01).

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes insipidus is defined as incapability to focus urine secondary to vasopressin deficiency or to vasopressin resistance which outcome is polyuria. The prevalence of DI is approximately 1:25,000 less than 10% of cases are hereditary naturally. Certainly diabetes insipidus is very infrequent. More than 90% of reported cases are from Central DI (CDI) depending on the cause it can occur at any age. Since now no hereditary prevalence of CDI has been confirmed. Whereas Nephrogenic DI is less resistant than CDI. DI can be defined as CDI or NDI [1]. In the magnocellular neurons of the paraventricular and supraoptic nuclei of the hypothalamus Vasopressin is produced which send axons to the posterior pituitary. The vasopressin is then excreted into the bloodstream via posterior pituitary. The neurons which release vasopressin are damaged in case of CDI. Whereas in case of NDI, there is normal production of vasopressin but at kidney level there is no response of the hormone. At the basolateral membrane of the collecting duct of the kidney Vasopressin acts at V2 receptors. Vasopressin triggers these receptors which provide the route to insertion of aquaporin 2 (AQP2) channels along the apical cell membrane [2]. There is more common impairment of V2R than the AQP2 channels are present in case of NDI. CDI include developmental abnormalities of the pituitary gland which are non-heritable and there causes are still unknown includes trauma or hypoxic injury causing disruption of supporting blood vessels, mechanical destruction by an intracranial tumor, pituitary inflammation or infection, pituitary gland infiltration. Several types of DI can be temporary whereas others are everlasting. CDI which are forms of heritable they can be autosomal dominant or recessive [3]. After the first year of life the more common autosomal dominant form typically appears which results in toxic accumulation of vasopressin precursors in the endoplasmic reticulum. On normal vasopressin molecules the mutant hormone endeavor a dominant negative effect. The presentation of Autosomal recessive CDI and of NDI is indistinguishable. However, Autosomal recessive CDI is infrequent and more prone to present within the initial three months after delivery [4]. Another form of inherited disorder from CDI is Wolfram syndrome. In the WFS1 gene there is a loss of function mutation that results in a very infrequent and progressive neurodegenerative disease. Classic Wolfram Syndrome Type 1 contains non-autoimmune diabetes mellitus, optic atrophy, and CDI.

In Wolfram Syndrome Type 2 the clinical representation is alike but does not have DI whereas

WST2 is rare. In Wolfram Syndrome the Management of CDI pursues the same rules for the treatment as for other causes of CDI [5]. Septo-optic dysplasia (SOD) could be a part of CDI, it is a condition in which there is hyperplasia of optic nerve, abnormal septum pellucidum, and deficiency of anterior and/or posterior pituitary hormone function. Over 50% of children complain to have unusual thirst in clinical settings of SOD, the percentage of thirst higher than abnormal thirst than with other types of DI. As explained earlier the number of CNS tumors could generate DI [6]. In approximately 55% of patients, Craniopharyngioma is a relatively common tumor producing CDI. Growth failure and DI are the combinations which confer Craniopharyngioma. More than 42% affected children have Langerhans Cell Histiocytosis (LCH) results in DI. 80% of children have intracranial germinomas associated with DI [7]. Children suffering from DI must have polyuric and polydipsic. They represents with utmost thirst with severe in search of water and vigorously favor cold water. A small experimental study was done to find out the suppression of vasopressin in dehydrated patients. Ice glaze versus tap water was given to them which conclude that the cold temperature of ingested liquid may play a role in satiation of thirst and also appears to suppress vasopressin in dehydrated, hyperosmolar patients without DI [8]. Polyuria is defined as one of the following: urine output (UOP) greater than 2 L/m²/day, 150 ml/kg/day in neonates, 100e110 ml/kg/day in children up to age 2, and 40e50 ml/kg/day in older children [9]. New onset enuresis in previously toilet-trained patients should raise suspicion of DI (or of diabetes mellitus). Most of the children are presented with supplementary sign and symptoms because of effects of intracranial neoplasms on brain structures and to effects on other pituitary axes. Growth retardation, fatigue, headache, emesis and visual field deficits have been described as presenting symptoms [10]. Slowed weight gain and linear growth may result from a child's strong preference for water, limiting the intake of more caloric liquids or solids, or from accompanying growth hormone deficiency. Children having any of these sign or symptoms should be assessed for DI. Once polyuria has confirmed, laboratory workup should include serum osmolality (S_{osm}), serum sodium, potassium, glucose, calcium, and blood urea nitrogen, urine osmolality (U_{osm}), urine specific gravity, and urine glucose. Diabetes mellitus or hypercalcemia-induced NDI can be ruled out by Normal serum glucose and calcium because of polyuria [11]. Normal serum potassium excludes hypokalemia induced NDI and normal BUN makes intrinsic renal disease less likely. A S_{osm} greater than 300 mOsm/kg at the same time

as an inappropriately dilute urine ($U_{osm} < 300$ mOsm/kg) is indicative of DI. In contrast, if $U_{osm} > 600$ mOsm/kg the patient is unlikely to have DI. If levels are indeterminate, such as $S_{osm} < 300$ with a $U_{osm} < 600$ and clinical suspicion of DI remains, further work-up is needed [12]. In observing clinical settings a water deprivation test is used to confirm the diagnosis of DI should always be performed everywhere. Water deprivation tests are not recommended to perform at home. The goal of the test is to observe the patient's urine concentrating ability and to assess the response to vasopressin. The test is usually begun overnight, and the child deprived of all liquids. Baseline weight, pulse, and blood pressure are obtained and followed hourly [13]. Serum sodium, U_{osm} , urine specific gravity, effect on normal vasopressin molecules. Serum BUN and plasma vasopressin can be obtained at baseline and at the conclusion of the test. If the patient develops clinical signs of hypovolemia at any point or if the weight loss is $>5\%$ of the starting weight, the test should be terminated. If the U_{osm} is > 1000 mOsm/kg once or >600 mOsm/kg and stable (within 30 mOsm/kg) for two consecutive voids, the test is stopped, and the patient does not have DI. If the S_{osm} is > 300 mOsm/kg and the $U_{osm} < 600$ mOsm/kg, the patient has DI and 1 unit/m² subcutaneous vasopressin should be given. UOP and S_{osm} should then be measured. In a patient with CDI, UOP should fall quickly and U_{osm} should rise, typically doubling. In a patient with NDI, UOP, U_{osm} and S_{osm} will not change. Obtaining first-morning S_{osm} , U_{osm} , and serum sodium can also be used to suggest DI. In DI, the first morning S_{osm} will be hyperosmolar (>295 mOsm/kg), urine will be hypoosmolar 143 mEq/L. A concentrated U_{osm} (>600 mOsm/kg) indicates that DI is not present. It is important to not alter the patient's water intake when examining serum and urine sodium and osmolality except when the patient is under observation as described above [14]. If CDI is confirmed, an MRI of the brain and pituitary is recommended. Other pituitary hormone axes should also be screened given increased risk for developing anterior pituitary hormone deficits; growth hormone deficiency is the most common. Classic findings of CDI on MRI include a thickened pituitary stalk or absence of the posterior pituitary bright spot. The presence of these findings is not a requisite for the diagnosis of DI. Lack of a posterior pituitary bright spot can be seen in CDI or in untreated NDI due to the body's release of stored vasopressin; it is not specific for CDI. The posterior bright spot is absent in 10% of normal newborn children, and the percentage increases by 1% per year of age [15]. In cases of acquired CDI where the MRI does not show a mass or lesion,

current recommendations are to continue screening with MRI for a minimum of 3 years. Screening frequency can be determined by the clinical index of suspicion; often, follow-up MRI is done at 3 months and 6 months from CDI diagnosis. If no significant change is detected, MRI is repeated at 6 month intervals. In 61 patients with new onset DI without an established etiology, were eventually diagnosed with a CNS germinoma, 4 with LCH, and 43 with idiopathic DI. Dose of DDAVP is used, and individual response is assessed; both dose and frequency are determined based on individual response to medication. Patients should be allowed to void prior to repeat doses in order to excrete waste. Excretion of a typical solute load in a normal individual requires urine production of 6e10 ml/kg/day [16]. Under full antidiuretic effect of vasopressin, U_{osm} of 1000 mOsm/kg can be achieved, and excessive fluid intake can lead to hyponatremia [17]. The most common side effect of DDAVP is hyponatremia which can be avoided by allowing for adequate breakthrough UOP. Breakthrough can be defined as >4 ml/kg/hr of urine for 2 or more hours, specific gravity.

Normally, vasopressin is secreted at a S_{osm} of 285 mOsm/kg, and thirst is triggered at a S_{osm} of 290 mOsm/kg. However, some individuals with DI fail to have appropriate thirst when S_{osm} rises, leading to life-threatening hypernatremia or hyponatremia with inappropriate fluid consumption at lower serum osmolalities [18]. In contrast, one third of patients who develop DI following craniopharyngioma resection are adipsic with disruption of both osmotic and non-osmotic pathways, demonstrated by a lack of thirst after administration of a hypertonic saline infusion or a fall in blood pressure [19]. Management has been successful using a fixed daily fluid regimen with DDAVP administered at doses allowing for appropriate UOP. Fluid amounts require regular adjustment with weight gain. Patients are weighed when eunatremic and a fluid regimen is determined based on maintenance requirements and estimated insensible losses. Fluid intake is adjusted based on daily weights, adding or subtracting 1 liter per 1 kg change in weight [20]. For example, if an ideal weight is 60 kg with daily fluid intake of 1.5 L and the patient now weighs 61 kg, the fluid intake would decrease by 1 L. During times of illness, fluid requirements may acutely vary, necessitating closer monitoring and more frequent sodium checks to maintain hydration and normonatremia.

Diagnosing and establishing the etiology of DI can be difficult. Once confirmed, management of polyuria and polydipsia poses its own challenges. After the

diagnosis of CDI is made, MRI of the pituitary, screening of all anterior pituitary hormones for associated hormonal deficits and appropriate further work up based on results should be performed. The mainstay of treatment in children with CDI remains administration of DDAVP to maintain sodium homeostasis and improve quality of life. In infants with DI, the literature supports use of thiazide diuretics as a safer alternative to DDAVP because they are dependent on liquid for nutrition and lack free access to fluids. Management of DI in patients requiring intravenous fluids needs further attention as no evidence based studies exist to determine optimal fluid choice and fluid rates. NDI is currently managed with thiazide diuretics; however additional research is necessary to optimize management and promising alternatives are on the horizon.

REFERENCE:

1. Di Iorgi N, Napoli F, Allegri AE, et al. Diabetes insipidus diagnosis and management. *Horm Res Paediatr* 2012;77(2): 69e84.
2. Fujiwara TM, Bichet DG. Molecular biology of hereditary diabetes insipidus. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2005;16(10):2836e46.
3. Kumar S. Wolfram syndrome: important implications for pediatricians and pediatric endocrinologists. *Pediatr Diabetes* 2010;11(1):28e37.
4. Rigoli L, Di Bella C. Wolfram syndrome 1 and Wolfram syndrome 2. *Curr Opin Pediatr* 2012;24(4):512e7.
5. Boutzios G, Livadas S, Marinakis E, et al. Endocrine and metabolic aspects of the Wolfram syndrome. *Endocrine* 2011; 40(1):10e3.
6. Hoyt WF, Kaplan SL, Grumbach MM, et al. Septo-optic dysplasia and pituitary dwarfism. *Lancet* 1970;1(7652):893e4.
7. Masera N, Grant DB, Stanhope R, et al. Diabetes insipidus with impaired osmotic regulation in septo-optic dysplasia and agenesis of the corpus callosum. *Arch Dis Child* 1994;70(1):51e3.
8. Cohen M, Bartels U, Branson H, et al. Trends in treatment and outcomes of pediatric craniopharyngioma, 1975-2011. *Neuro Oncol* 2013;15(6):767e74.
9. Dunger DB, Broadbent V, Yeoman E, et al. The frequency and natural history of diabetes insipidus in children with Langerhans-cell histiocytosis. *N Engl J Med* 1989;321(17):1157e62.
10. Jorsal T, Rorth M. Intracranial germ cell tumours. A review with special reference to endocrine manifestations. *Acta Oncol* 2012;51(1):3e9.
11. Salata RA, Verbalis JG, Robinson AG. Cold water stimulation of oropharyngeal receptors in man inhibits release of vasopressin. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab* 1987;65(3):561e7.
12. Sperling M. *Pediatric endocrinology*. 4 ed. Philadelphia, PA: Elsevier; 2014.
13. Maghnie M, Cosi G, Genovese E, et al. Central diabetes insipidus in children and young adults. *N Engl J Med* 2000;343(14): 998e1007.
14. Frasier SD, Kutnik LA, Schmidt RT, et al. A water deprivation test for the diagnosis of diabetes insipidus in children. *Am J Dis Child* 1967;114(2):157e60.
15. Richman RA, Post EM, Notman DD, et al. Simplifying the diagnosis of diabetes insipidus in children. *Am J Dis Child* 1981; 135(9):839e41.
16. Rivkees SA, Dunbar N, Wilson TA. The management of central diabetes insipidus in infancy: desmopressin, low renal solute load formula, thiazide diuretics. *J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab* 2007;20(4):459e69.
17. Srivatsa AM, Joseph. *Pediatric endocrinology*. 2 ed. CRC Press; 2006.
18. Karthikeyan A, Abid N, Sundaram PC, et al. Clinical characteristics and management of cranial diabetes insipidus in infants. *J Pediatr Endocrinol Metab* 2013;26(11e12):1041e6.
19. Robson WL, Leung AK, Norgaard JP. The comparative safety of oral versus intranasal desmopressin for the treatment of children with nocturnal enuresis. *J Urol* 2007;178(1):24e30.
20. Loffing J. Paradoxical antidiuretic effect of thiazides in diabetes insipidus: another piece in the puzzle. *J Am Soc Nephrol* 2004;15(11):2948e50.